

OOPSLA Artifact - Paper #194

VESPA: Static Profiling for Binary Optimization

September 13, 2021

1 Introduction

This artifact contains the VESPA tool as described in the paper, as well as scripts to reproduce the experiments mentioned in each of the research questions. Everything is packaged in a Docker image. We used Docker instead of a Virtual Machine to facilitate the distribution of the artifact. Be aware that since some of our benchmarks are proprietary, you may not reproduce the experiments exactly alike the ones exposed in the paper, but you should achieve similar results. Furthermore, we observed that database management systems and their benchmarks do not work properly inside a docker container, thus you may have not see the same behaviour for performance improvements, but you should observe the same behaviour for correlation and icache misses that you read in the paper.

2 Set up

To set up the artifact, one should first pull the Docker image from DockerHUB. The image is available in the URL <https://hub.docker.com/r/angelicamoreira/oopsla21artifact/>, under the tag *vespa*. The image is based on a fresh Ubuntu 18.04 image, which we set up with all the necessary dependencies to run our experiments. The following example shows how to download it through the Docker command line:

```
angelica@opencl:~# sudo docker pull
  angelicamoreira/oopsla21artifact:vespa
```

Note that the download might take a while. However, the Docker command line should show the progress as it downloads. Once the image has

been downloaded, one can run a container for the image in interactive mode (-it flags) to start up the environment with a root shell inside it and with privileges to run the linux perf tool ¹:

```
angelica@opencl:~# sudo docker run -it --privileged
  angelicamoreira/oopsla21artifact:vespa /bin/bash
```

These are the only necessary steps to set up the environment. Once the container is running and the user has access to a shell within it, all the experiments can be performed/replicated from the shell itself. The next few sections detail step-by-step how to reproduce experiments for each of the research questions mentioned in the paper.

3 Step-by-step

3.1 RQ1 – Accuracy

To replicate the experiments for the first research question, one must first navigate to the directory dedicated to that section:

```
angelica@opencl:~# cd /home/oopsla21_artifact/rq1
angelica@opencl:/home/oopsla21_artifact/rq1#
```

That directory contains a bash script which should execute all the steps required to run the experiment and display its results. One can simply call the script like so:

```
angelica@opencl:/home/oopsla21_artifact/rq1# bash RQ1.sh
```

The script should take a few minutes to execute. It first performs predictions for each of the classification models described, then generates a comparison chart named RQ1_Comparison_ESP_VESPA.pdf. Its initial output should look like the following:

¹It is advisable to execute the install_perf.sh script at the root folder (homeoopsla21_artifact) inside the running docker container before running the research questions' scripts.

```
angelica@opencl:/home/oopspla21_artifact/rq1# bash RQ1.sh

Charts were saved at: /home/oopspla21_artifact/rq1/result/
RQ1_Comparison_ESP_VESPA.pdf
...
```

Once done, it should display the results of the experiment as seen in Table 3 of the paper:

```
(vespa-env) angelica@opencl:/home/oopspla21_artifact/rq1#
  BINARY  ESP DTR  VESPA DTR  VESPA DNN
0    GCC   0.23    0.21    0.18
1   CLANG  0.20    0.18    0.20
2   MYSQL  0.28    0.26    0.23
3 POSTGRES 0.25    0.22    0.21
```

3.2 RQ2 – Speedup

This second research question involved measuring the performance improvements and regressions of binaries optimized using different profile information. For this section we are not providing the same charts as the paper, but instead a table for each benchmark with its performance runtime summarized. To reproduce the experiments for the second research question you must, like previously, navigate to the directory dedicated to that research question:

```
angelica@opencl:~# cd /home/oopspla21_artifact/rq2
angelica@opencl:/home/oopspla21_artifact/rq2#
```

That directory contains the bash script which will execute all the steps required to run the experiments and display its results. You can simply call the script like the following:

```
angelica@opencl:/home/oopspla21_artifact/rq2# bash RQ2.sh
```

This may take a while (around 20hrs) depending on the machine you're using to run this docker image. Its output will be something like the following:

```
angelica@opencl:/home/oopspla21_artifact/rq2# bash RQ2.sh
===== [END] COLLECTING DATA FROM BENCHMARKS' EXECUTION
```

```
=====
```

	Binary	Speedup_CLANG
	iCache_Misses_CLANG \	
0	BOLT+Dynamic Profile (Baseline)	0.382148
		0.448481
1	BOLT+Limited Dynamic Profile	0.173936
		0.272889
2	BOLT+VESPA	0.083007
		0.173235
3	BOLT+Calder	0.034639
		0.106442
4	BOLT+Wu Larus	0.048238
		0.108242
5	BOLT+Unbiased	0.023901
		0.061592
6	BOLT+No Profile	0.053157
		0.122188
7	BOLT+Never	-0.045645
		0.020925
8	BOLT+Always	-0.064212
		0.015542

	Speedup_GCC	iCache_Misses_GCC	TPS_Improvement_MySQL
	iCache_Misses_MySQL \		
0	0.202048	0.407166	0.086347
	0.134551		
1	0.080416	0.211178	0.031600
	0.092860		
2	0.018963	0.101443	0.021920
	0.015631		
3	0.010323	0.075500	0.009511
	0.022899		
4	0.014403	0.061142	0.001979
	-0.012213		
5	0.015318	0.071180	-0.012931
	-0.013783		
6	0.019846	0.083536	-0.000320
	-0.016404		
7	-0.049707	-0.009982	-0.083052
	-0.053292		
8	-0.088355	-0.071861	-0.137124
	-0.134854		

```

TPS_Improvement_PostgreSQL  iCache_Misses_PostgreSQL  \
0          0.249172          0.297921
1          0.124985          0.186060
2         -0.023449          0.045094
3         -0.030071          0.021568
4         -0.033718          0.009267
5         -0.018158          0.040492
6         -0.033526          0.016550
7         -0.063735         -0.013962
8         -0.107526         -0.092970

Performance_Improvements_GEOMEAN  iCache_Misses_GEOMEAN
0          0.225369          0.332378
1          0.101472          0.193301
2          0.024414          0.085863
3          0.005831          0.057297
4          0.007299          0.042764
5          0.001872          0.040424
6          0.009299          0.053035
7         -0.060649         -0.013736
8         -0.099701         -0.069599
Output csv file was saved at:
/home/oopsla21_artifact/rq2/RQ2_Comparison_Table.csv

```

3.3 RQ3 – Correlation

This third research question involved checking the correlation between performance improvements and L1-Cache Misses, in order to help us to verify if our hypothesis that our gains with VESPA are due to BOLT’s code alignment algorithm. To run this experiment one must do the following:

```

angelica@opencl:~# cd /home/oopsla21_artifact/rq3
angelica@opencl:/home/oopsla21_artifact/rq3# bash RQ3.sh

```

The expected output after running this script should be something like the following:

```
angelica@opencl1://home/oops1a21_artifact/rq3# bash RQ3.sh
```

```
===== Clang scores =====
```

```
Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.992  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Spearman's correlation coefficient: 0.983  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Kendall correlation coefficient: 0.957  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
===== GCC scores =====
```

```
Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.993  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Spearman's correlation coefficient: 0.919  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Kendall correlation coefficient: 0.867  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.002
```

```
===== MySQL scores =====
```

```
Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.944  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Spearman's correlation coefficient: 0.958  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Kendall correlation coefficient: 0.899  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.001
```

```
===== PostgreSQL scores =====
```

```
Pearson correlation coefficient: 0.993  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Spearman's correlation coefficient: 0.983  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.000
```

```
Kendall correlation coefficient: 0.956  
Samples are correlated (reject H0) p=0.001
```

```
Charts were saved at:
```

```
  /home/oops1a21_artifact/rq3/RQ3_Correlation.pdf
```

3.4 RQ4 – Training

The fourth research question involved measuring the time necessary for instrumenting the binaries, gathering profile information, extracting program features, preprocessing and merging those files, encoding and then training VESPA’s ML model. To do so, we provide a script that automates this process. At the end of the script’s run, it will report the elapsed time, in seconds for each of these steps. To run this reserach question one must do the following:

```
angelica@opencl:~# cd /home/oopsla21_artifact/rq4
angelica@opencl:/home/oopsla21_artifact/rq4# bash RQ4.sh
```

The expected output after running this script should be something like the following:

```
...
===== END OF TRAINING VESPA TASK =====
===== STAR OF PRINTIG RESULTS =====
Instrumentation: Using BOLT to generate instrumented version of
  each of the 237 programs in our training set takes 3 seconds.
Profiled execution: Executing each instrumented binary and
  collecting dynamic profiles takes 19158 seconds.
Feature extraction: Running BOLT with the feature miner pass to
  collect static features for all the binaries takes 6 seconds.
Preprocessing and merging: Preprocessing all the static feature
  files and merging them takes 37 seconds.
Encoding and training: Encoding features and training the Deep
  Neural Network with the entire branch dataset takes 5281
  seconds.
===== END OF PRINTIG RESULTS =====
```

3.5 RQ5 – Application

The last research question was in regards to measuring the total time taken to generate binaries for each optimization process, and check how VESPA fares in regards to its competitors. To run this research question one must do the following:

```
angelica@opencl: cd /home/oopsla21_artifact/rq5
angelica@opencl:/home/oopsla21_artifact/rq5# bash RQ5.sh
```

The expected output after running this script should be something like the following:

```
angelica@opencl:/home/oopsla21_artifact/rq5# bash RQ5.sh
      Binary  PostgreSQL  MySQL  GCC  Clang
0  BOLT+DynamicProfile(Baseline)      23   502  892  3255
1    BOLT+LimitedDynamicProfile      36   506  913  3296
2          BOLT+VESPA                96    67  306   743
3          BOLT+Calder                75    65  285   718
4          BOLT+WuLarus               16    52   62   139
5          BOLT+Unbiased              10    40   51   100
6          BOLT+NoProfile              6    30   22    51
7          BOLT+Never                 10    40   29    71
8          BOLT+Always                 8    39   28    71
```